

SDS-PAGE ANALYSIS OF PROTEIN IN MUSCLE AND HEAD KIDNEY OF *LABEO ROHITA* IN RESPONSE TO AEROMONIASIS

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ABSTRACT

Aeromonas infections are regarded as the most common bacterial infections in fresh water fish and fish suffering due to aeromoniasis show external symptoms like hemorrhages at the base of fins or on the skin, distended abdomen and protruding eyes. *Labeo rohita*, one of the most important freshwater Indian major carp is selected to understand the pathogenic effects of *Aeromonas liquefaciens*. Five groups of experimental fish (65-75 gm wt) were employed in this work. 12 fish in each group were infected intramuscularly @ 10^{-2} CFU/Fish (group A), 10^{-4} CFU/Fish (group B), 10^{-6} CFU/Fish (group C), $10^{-2} + 10^{-2}$ CFU/Fish (group D) and $10^{-3} + 10^{-3}$ CFU/Fish (group E); 12 fish were kept as uninfected control (group F) for comparison. Six fish from each infected group and controls were necropsies at hour 24 and 96 tissues of muscle and head kidney were separated and analyzed for protein profile by SDS-PAGE analysis. The protein bands in muscle and head kidney showed remarkable changes in the experimental groups of fish (groups A, B, C, D and E treated with *A. liquefaciens*) on day 1 to 4 of experimental period due to the sensitization of bacterial antigens.

Key words: SDS-PAGE, protein, muscle, head kidney, *Labeo rohita*, aeromoniasis.

INTRODUCTION

Aeromonas liquefaciens is widely distributed pathogenic bacteria in warm water fish throughout the world (Sarkar et al., 2000). Aeromonad sps cause tail and fin rot, hemorrhagic septicemia, red mouth, swollen abdomen etc. in intensive culture systems of fish. Pathogenic *A. hydrophila* were found to be associated in five carp species namely *Labeo rohita*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Cirrhinus cirrprolus*, *Catla catla* and *Hypothalamicthys molitrix* (Dolly et al., 1986, Torres et al., 1990, Roberts et al., 1990). Hasan et al., and Islam et al., (2008) studied experimental pathogenesis of aeromoniasis in liver and kidney of farmed fish. Aeromoniasis is identified as a serious disease in cat fishes, carps and perch (Sarkar and Rashid,

2012). Impairment of hematological findings have been reported in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) during saprolegniasis (Singh et al., 2013). Intramuscular injection of *A. hydrophila* caused much pathogenicity in liver and kidney of *Anabas testudineus* (Hossain et al., 2011). The important physiological mechanism that protects the fish against the microbial infections is called immunity and very little is known about the immune system of Indian major carps (Ingram, 1980). Many immune cells and their products contribute to the defense mechanism of fish; the elevation and or decrement of these serve as indicators of stress response and / or disease resistance (Anderson and Seviki, 1995; Sahoo and Mukherjee, 2003; Sahoo et al., 2005). Skin/muscle is the nonspecific component of the natural immunity and the head kidney. Since

head kidney serves as a major lymphoid organ in addition to thymus and spleen (Press and Evenson 1999 and Madhuri et al, 2013), a new vista has been opened to study the protein profile by SDS PAGE in the skin and kidney of freshwater *Labeo rohita* exposed to varied doses of *A. liquefaciens*

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Labeo rohita (6 months old; 65–75 gm wt) are procured and acclimatized to laboratory conditions. All the experimental and control fish were fed with commercial pellet diet. Virulent strain of *A. liquefaciens* was obtained from MTCC, Chandigarh; fresh cultures were prepared from parent culture and infective doses were made following standard methods. Five groups of experimental fish were employed in this work. Twelve fish were infected intramuscularly @ 10^{-2} CFU/fish (Group A), 12 with 10^{-4} CFU/fish(Group B), 12 with 10^{-6} CFU/fish (Group C), 12 with repeated doses of $10^{-2} + 10^{-2}$ CFU/fish at 5day interval (Group D) and 12 with $10^{-3}+10^{-3}$ CFU/fish (Group E). 12fish were kept as uninfected control (Group F). Six fish from each infected group and controls were necropsied at hour 24 and 96 of experimental period. Tissues of muscle and head kidney were separated and analyzed by SDS PAGE for protein profile following standard methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SDS-PAGE analysis of muscle and head kidney showed definite qualitative alterations in protein fractions and in their intensity profiles on day 1 and 4 of infection.

Protein profile of muscle:

The muscle tissue at hour 24 and 96 showed a series of several protein bands ranging between 8.316 to 114.390 KDa of the marker (Figures-1A,1B). The protein fractions within a range of 8.316 to 110.610 KDa are more visible in the muscle electropherogram on day 1 of infection (Figure 1 and Table 1). The experimental fish, *L. rohita* appeared sensitive to the increased doses of pathogen, *A. liquefaciens*. In single and

repeated doses of infection, maximum variations are seen in the muscle protein profile; synthesis of additional protein fractions was induced on day 1 of infection. Similarly, on day 4 of infection, the protein fractions were ranged between 0.437 to 107.62 KDa in muscle (Figure 1B and Table 2). Additional protein fractions were synthesized on day 4 of infection in all the experimental groups A, B, C, D and E.

Figure-1. Electropherogram of protein profile of muscle in *L. rohita* (Fig-1A: on hour 24 and Fig-1B: on hour 96) infected with various doses of *A. liquefaciens*.

(0- protein marker; 1- control; 2- 10^{-2} CFU/fish; 3- 10^{-4} CFU/fish; 4- 10^{-6} CFU/fish; 5- $10^{-2}+10^{-2}$ CFU/fish; 6- $10^{-3}+10^{-3}$ CFU/fish)

Fig-1A

Fig-1B

Table-1. Protein profile of muscle of *L. rohita* (on hour 24) infected with various doses of *A. liquafaciens*

Molecular weight (KDa)	Control	Infective doses (CFU/fish)				
		10 ⁻²	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁶	10 ⁻² +10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³ +10 ⁻³
110.610	97.000+++	114.390	98.512	99.268	96.417	100.024
100.780	66.000++	104.561	89.201	90.456	84.525	90.456
91.683	40.000++	92.887	81.593	78.424	55.839	83.086
83.086	35.000++	81.593	67.091	63.416	39.310	55.839
69.199	25.000++	63.416	49.987	45.803	36.960	39.310
45.803	20.000++	39.310	38.624	38.454	35.000	36.483
36.960	14.000+	36.326	34.362	34.637	32.533	33.891
34.909		33.987	32.647	31.675	30.988	32.417
33.498		33.085	31.409	28.648	29.735	30.542
29.026		30.843	28.648	26.509	27.418	27.197
20.256		26.743	26.270	19.044	24.179	23.614
16.336		17.994	19.044	16.478	20.785	15.594
14.715		15.594	15.943	14.649	14.586	14.282
14.039		14.420	14.472	13.964	14.085	13.947
13.956		13.975	14.039	13.945	13.934	13.053
13.684		13.977	13.945	13.526	12.974	11.000
12.026		12.974	13.684	12.342	11.079	9.105
10.526		11.395	12.895	11.395	9.579	
9.342		10.132	11.711	10.447		
8.316		8.947	10.211	9.500		
			8.711	8.632		

Protein profile of kidney:

The kidney tissue at hour 24 and 96 showed a series of several protein bands ranging between 9.333 to 152.800 KDa of the marker (Figure-2A and 2B). The head kidney electropherogram showed varied protein fractions within a range of 9.333 to 152.800 kDa (on day 1) and 9.920 to 126.529 KDa (on day 4) (Tables-3 and 4). The infective doses (both single and repeated) sensitized the fish and induced changes in protein profile in head kidney. It is clear that in all the experimental groups (A, B, C, D and E) of fish, additional protein fractions were synthesized on day 1 and 4 of infection in head kidney.

The alterations in protein profile in muscle and head kidney of test fish may indicate that the fish are prone to stress due to Aeromoniasis causing marked alteration in the protein bands. Begum (2004) also found biochemical alterations in muscle tissue of *Clarius batracus* during insecticide treatment. Various authors (Boone

Figure-2. Electropherogram of protein profile of head kidney in *L. rohita* (Fig-2A: on hour 24 and Fig-2B: on hour 96) infected with various doses of *A. liquefaciens*.

(0- protein marker; 1- control; 2- 10⁻² CFU/fish; 3- 10⁻⁴ CFU/fish; 4- 10⁻⁶ CFU/fish; 5- 10⁻²+10⁻² CFU/fish; 6- 10⁻³+10⁻³ CFU/fish)

Fig-2A

Fig-2B

and Vijayan, 2002; Tabche *et al.*, 2002; Ali *et al.*, 2003) reported synthesis of stress proteins due to heavy metal treatment. In the present study, pathogenic aeromonads were found as

effective inducers of stress protein in altering the tissue protein fractions of experimental fish (exposed to various doses of *A. liquefaciens*). The primary mechanism of infection/disease involves protein denaturation which results in molecular aggregation and misfolding as evidenced by Hightower (1991). Synthesis of stress protein is also explained as a protective and repairing mechanism; synthesis of stress proteins might have occurred to facilitate the repair of denatured proteins in aeromoniasis.

Infectious pathogens cause acute, chronic and latent forms of disease depending upon the virulence of the pathogen and susceptibility of the fish, mode of administration, and duration of exposure. Physiological status of the fish may inhibit the infectivity of disease causing pathogens by nonspecific immune mechanisms. Bacterial pathogens produce ill effects in the fresh water fish at physiological, tissue, cellular and molecular level as suggested by Das and

Table-2. Protein profile of muscle (on hour 96) of *L. rohita* infected with various doses of *A. liquefaciens*

	Molecular weight (KDa)	Control	Infective doses (CFU/fish)				
			10 ⁻²	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁶	10 ⁻² +10 ⁻²	10 ⁻³ +10 ⁻³
1	107.62	98.564	117.450	96.501	130.670	121.216	114.106
2	103.24	72.096	102.570	95.724	125.421	117.226	103.402
3	94.63	43.072	97.674	93.120	110.262	111.276	74.216
4	80.09	36.267	84.967	89.100	90.561	101.412	90.222
5	70.23	29.670	67.412	87.120	95.264	95.246	84.936
6	47.962	20.517	36.210	62.410	93.277	82.364	82.914
7	39.892	13.520	34.612	57.670	86.216	79.932	89.624
8	37.506		33.421	53.120	82.312	64.437	79.0572
9	33.498		30.20	50.100	71.261	60.964	65.471
10	27.06		27.659	37.107	62.217	59.822	40.761
11	21.25		28.400	26.101	60.212	56.932	38.461
12	17.664		16.43	23.156	57.226	49.214	28.671
13	14.62		18.400	19.460	50.121	47.314	23.441
14	12.09		16.806	17.560	45.212	42.713	19.240
15	12.08		15.491	16.110	41.647	39.991	17.470
16	11.977		14.201	15.172	37.214	35.724	13.450
17	0.956		13.061	13.192	35.228	30.403	12.100
18	0.742		12.960	12.105	32.418	28.904	9.56
19	0.656		11.360	9.121	20.621	19.464	
20	0.554		10.140	8.21	11.712	12.334	
21	0.437		7.60	6.440	6.212	6.784	

Table-3. Protein profile of head kidney (on hour 24) of *L. rohita* infected with various doses of *A. liquefaciens*.

	Molecular weight (KDa)	Control	Infective doses (CFU/fish)				
			10^{-2}	10^{-4}	10^{-6}	$10^{-2}+10^{-2}$	$10^{-3}+10^{-3}$
1	152.800	131.800	66.000	150.000	127.600	95.400	43.377
2	143.000	117.800	45.000	131.800	95.400	81.400	41.861
3	131.800	45.000	35.000	112.200	78.600	67.400	39.901
4	115.000	42.811	25.000	94.000	68.800	42.811	37.000
5	77.200	41.141	20.000	49.753	41.861	41.861	31.969
6	53.847	37.000	14.000	43.377	35.000	39.438	24.726
7	43.643	31.126		40.122	21.334	35.356	22.094
8	37.302	28.709		31.126	19.633	31.126	21.334
9	32.396	22.566		25.584	18.066	23.971	20.593
10	29.492	20.216		22.244	16.809	22.401	19.927
11	23.112	18.710		20.758	14.444	20.438	18.471
12	20.144	16.894		19.707	13.250	19.633	15.856
13	18.868	15.856		18.066	10.917	18.066	14.267
14	17.234	14.267		16.031		15.681	12.917
15	16.118	9.333		15.153		14.710	10.417
16	15.241			14.000		13.167	
17	14.355			13.167		11.167	
18	11.000			12.250			
19	9.333			10.833			

Table-4. Protein profile of head kidney (on hour 96) of *L. rohita* infected with various doses of *A. liquefaciens*.

	Molecular weight (KDa)	Control	Infective doses (CFU/fish)				
			10^{-2}	10^{-4}	10^{-6}	$10^{-2}+10^{-2}$	$10^{-3}+10^{-3}$
1	126.529	124.059	66.000	45.931	46.918	80.824	43.715
2	111.706	111.706	45.000	44.063	43.593	55.081	42.122
3	96.882	50.175	35.000	41.368	37.656	43.203	40.493
4	80.824	43.467	25.000	29.497	33.970	41.759	36.959
5	72.176	36.592	20.000	24.676	22.426	39.479	23.287
6	44.063	30.940	14.000	21.612	20.772	36.592	20.696
7	38.913	26.455		20.188	20.441	29.497	20.188
8	32.946	21.479		19.632	19.575	22.242	19.457
9	28.128	19.632		18.290	18.058	20.284	15.803
10	21.906	18.874		15.895	17.149	19.575	14.288
11	18.943	17.405		13.600	16.080	17.979	12.960
12	17.320	15.616		11.120	14.670	15.429	11.040
13	15.988	14.575		9.520	13.200	14.575	
14	14.479	9.680			11.200	13.200	
15	11.600					10.960	
16	9.920						

Mukherjee (2003) and Begum (2004). When the fish is subjected to stress, a group of new or existing cellular protein synthesis may occur to combat the pathogenic effects. Such stress-oriented proteins are called as stress proteins. This stress response can be assessed by the tissue/organ damage. The alteration in tissue protein level could be an important clinical indicator test for tissue specific pathogenicity. The present investigations demonstrated that there were definite qualitative alterations in protein fractions and their intensity profiles in the muscle and head kidney.

The protein bands in muscle and head kidney also showed remarkable changes in the experimental groups of fish (groups A, B, C, D and E) treated with *A. liquefaciens* on day 1 and 4. These observations are similar to that of Udgate *et al.* (2006) who found that the antigens of *A. liquefaciens* produce a very good primary and secondary response by producing agglutinating antibodies in fish received pathogens orally.

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